

Quantum Bound States, Resolution, Information and Interference

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 4, 2020

Free quantum particles may be represented by a wavefunction of $\exp(ipx)$ where “ px ” suggests a resolution scale L with $p=2(3.14)\hbar/L$. In this note, we suggest that such a resolution may already be present in classical mechanics. $\exp(ipx)$ is a periodic form which incorporates this resolution and through a modulus of 1 ensures equal probability to be at any point x . In order to use $\exp(ipx)$, it seems that there must be a physical mechanics associated with the resolution.

Given that $\exp(ipx)=\cos(px) + i\sin(px)$, we argue that two different probability cycling or flows exist, one related to energy ($pp/2m$) and time and the other to flux- momentum and space i.e. $\sin(px)$. The link between the two is: $\cos(px)\cos(px)+\sin(px)\sin(px) = 1$ i.e. the two are out of phase. This appears to be similar to the two dimensions x and ict . Each cycle or flow has its own frequency with positive and negative mutually exclusive subdivisions within resolution pockets, $1/E$ for time and L with $p=2(3.14)\hbar/L$ for space. The frequencies are associated by positive and negative probabilities (linked perhaps with forward and backward motions etc) and lead to interference if one considers different momentum values.

We attempt to consider these issues in this note. In addition, we examine $\ln(W)$ representing information, with $W(x)$, being the wavefunction. The change in information is $-i dx \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$. Thus, it seems that momentum flow carries information in a quantum bound state.

“ px ” and Spatial Resolution

In quantum mechanics, px is associated with spatial resolution through $p= 2(3.14)\hbar/L$ with L being the characteristic length or wavelength. It seems, however, that ideas of resolution already exist in classical mechanics. Consider a one dimensional length divided into equal infinitesimal dx portions. A fast particle traverses dx in a much shorter time than a slow one, thus possible time measurement errors may be greater for the slow particle. In other words: $v(t+\delta t) - v(t) = dx/(t+\delta t) - dx/t \approx (dx/t)(1-\delta t/t)$. For a fast particle, t is small, so δt must be even smaller. Then $\delta x = v \delta t$ suggests a very small δx error for a fast particle. Thus, we argue that in classical physics, a small δx or high x resolution is required for fast particles. This seems to have nothing to do with quantum mechanics. It may also be noted, however, that in classical mechanics one does not usually consider an error at all. All quantities are known at each point in time and space.

This begs the question: Why is a large p not associated with a sharp resolution in time if there is a δt ? Why is a conversion made to δx and p associated with δx ? Note: p means motion through both space and time, but $p=0$ still means a clock is ticking. Thus, it seems spatial resolution is directly related to p with perhaps energy (rest mass in the $p=0$ case) linked to time resolution.

Given that one deals with x , t and p (momentum), one may create the Lorentz invariant: $Et-px$ which is the form appearing in the quantum free particle wavefunction:

$\exp(-i(Et-px))$ and again could already exist in classical physics if there were a reason to track the resolution. One may ask why $\exp(i \text{ phase})$ is used. We argue that it represents a statistical conditional probability showing the resolution associated with p and E , but has a modulus of 1 indicating that a particle with constant p in both classical physics and quantum physics has an equal probability of being found at any x . In classical physics, a real, constant number may be used to describe an equal probability to be at any x point. It seems there is no physical cycling related to the wavelength L and no reason to use $\exp(ipx)$ which appears to describe a “two-dimensional” effect. In other words, there is no Δx error term. In quantum mechanics, therefore, it seems that an “error” must exist perhaps due to internal motion such as zitterbewegung. In classical physics even in a stochastic case, a particle has a specific velocity at x , there is no error region.

We later describe ipx as information i.e. $\ln(\exp(ipx))$.

This begs the question: Why should there be interference in quantum bound states? We argue that in quantum mechanics there is perhaps a physical cycling associated with the cycling of the probability wave $\cos(px)+i\sin(px)$. In fact, if physical cycling were present in classical physics, a similar probability wave approach might apply (e.g. for sound or vibrating systems etc) as has been considered in the literature recently. (1) We later argue that $\cos(px)+i\sin(px)$ represent two separate probability cycles, $\cos(px)$ associated with energy-time resolution i.e. $pp/2m$ averages and $\sin(px)$ with space- p cycling i.e. p averages or space fluxes. The two are linked through $\cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px) = 1$, but it as if one has two very different statistical evolutions as $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ squared does not equal $\langle pp \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ in quantum mechanics.

Quantum State and Stochasticity

We argue that quantum motion is stochastic due to stochastic hits from a potential. If one considers motion in one direction, say the forward, we argue that at each x there is a momentum probability distribution (a different momentum at a different time). Using probabilities for these momenta, one may calculate average $pp/2m$ which must satisfy: $KE_{\text{ave}}(x) + V(x) = E$. If a particle is knocked backwards, but one is analyzing average forward motion, it is as if conditional probability and kinetic energy times probability $pp/2m$ $P(p/x)$ are lost. Thus, conditional probability may be both positive and negative suggesting that if one is to have a function, it should vary in magnitude as well. This seems to be critical because in forming regions of positive and negative pockets within a wavelength pocket, the probability drops to zero as one switches. This has physical implications in that there is no probability to find a particle at such a spot, i.e. there is density clumping. How could this result physically? The average bound state momentum at x is $-i dW/dx / W$. If W has a zero (i.e. no particles at x), the average momentum shoots to infinite. Thus, on average there is very large speed at such a point and one may have difficulty detecting the particle because it moves so quickly out of dx about this point.

A further consideration is the spatial resolution considered in the first section. There is a wavelength associated with spatial errors for a momentum p i.e. $\lambda = 2\pi\hbar/p$. It is not possible to have forward and backward motion within distances much smaller than the wavelength. An immediate question which arises is: What is the probability of moving forward relative to moving backward for a given p ? Above we considered forward average motion, but there is also backward average motion, thus forward and backward motion should be on equal footing suggesting a symmetric probability function. In a classical system, a particle at x may move forward or backward with p . The average is 0. There is no "error" in classical physics and no region within L of positive and then negative motion as if the average motion is spread from a point to the entire region L . Over the region L , the average of both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ in $\exp(ipx)$ are both 0. This suggests a physical cycling mechanism, we argue, paralleling the establishment of L length resolution pockets with forward or backward motions forced into mutually exclusive subregions within L .

The pattern within a pocket is further differentiated by the quantity being averaged. For example, for the average of $\pm p$ (with $a(p)=a(-p)$) one has: $a(p)^2 i \sin(px)$ while for $pp/2m$ with p/p : $a(p)^2 \cos(px)$ holds. Thus, the two parts of $\exp(ipx)$ seem to be linked to energy or time resolution and momentum or spatial resolution. These are kept "separate" by "i".

As noted, $\ln(\exp(ipx))=ipx$ may be thought of as information with a change d/dx proportional to p . $\ln(\exp(-iEt))=-iEt$ may also be considered information with a change d/dt proportional to $E=pp/2m$. Thus, $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ and $\langle pp/2m \text{ at } x \rangle$ are rates of change of time types of information. It is interesting to note that the imaginary "i" comes into play in "x" and "ict" in a similar manner.

In classical physics, x, t, p and $pp/2m$ are all directly linked because a time t is associated with $x, v(x)$ and $pp/2m$ at x . These variables are synchronized. In the quantum case, one has two different cycles of information flow, one related to time and energy and another to momentum and spatial flow. The two are linked, but out of phase. (It is also possible to have $1/2m ppp$ which is kinetic energy flux and associated with spatial flow). In classical physics, p and pp are directly related in one being the square of the other, but such is not the case for $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ and $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle$ in quantum mechanics. These two follow their own flows and so one needs two components $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$, which are nevertheless linked i.e. $\cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px) = 1$. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. The two stochastic flows, one in time and the other space seem to be "out of phase". Interference occurs as one considers one set of $\cos(px) + i\sin(px)$ with another $\cos(p_1x)+i\sin(p_1x)$ and tries to establish average probability cycling for the two different pieces i.e. time and space flow or cycling.

It may also be noted that interference occurs when one physically distinguishes between different momentum p scenarios. In fact, the idea seems to be that one could measure a bound particle and find that at the time of measurement it was in fact in a specific p state with a certain probability. Thus, one has a physical resonance with a distribution of momentum leading to $\langle p \text{ ave} \rangle$ and $\langle pp \text{ ave} \rangle$ at each x point, but one may mentally consider each momentum state p . Interference occurs because an average probability with both negative and positive values is assigned to the single p state. The overall average of different p 's should also have positive and negative conditional probability, although with a pattern suitable for the overall system.

One may object to positive and negative conditional probabilities (with x) for the overall p average i.e the total wavefunction, but the overall wavefunction should also have a resolution pattern. Consider adding total wavefunctions for two “mentally” distinguishable processes (i.e. distinguishable in classical physics). In such a case, the wavefunction for each consists of the p probabilities which may be both positive and negative. One does physically distinguish between the two processes, so if there is interference of p conditional probabilities within one wavefunction, and the other, there should be cross interference when the two processes are considered together with no physical distinguishability discerned.

A final consideration is to suggest that conditional probability(p,x) should appear as a free particle conditional probability $\exp(ipx)$ because one considers an ensemble of free particles. Stochastic hits allow for the different p values of each $\exp(ipx)$.

A question which arises is: What happens to $\exp(-i p p/2m t)$ associated with each free particle? We try to answer this in the next section.

$$W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle dx)$$

If one begins with a momentum distribution based on $a(p) \exp(ipx)$, then: $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. The translation operator $\exp[dx d/dx]$ utilizes d/dx , an operator which returns ip when operating on $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, a translation of $W(x)$ is directly related to the average momentum at x i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} W(x+dx) &= W(x) + dx d/dx W(x) = W(x) + dx \text{ Sum over } p i a(p) p \exp(ipx) \\ &= W(x) (1+i(-i)dx d/dx \ln(W)) \text{ approx} = W(x) \exp(i dx \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle) \quad ((1)) \end{aligned}$$

A question arises: Is one able to obtain ((1)) without making use of $\exp(ipx)$?

$$W(x) = \exp(\ln(W)) \quad ((2))$$

Traditionally, $\ln(W)$ is called information if W is a probability. We call $W(x)$ a relative conditional probability. Then:

$$W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i (-i) dx d \ln(W) /dx) \quad ((3))$$

$dx d/dx \ln(W)$ is a change in information. In the first section, we argued that there exists a certain Δx uncertainty associated with each p i.e. L from $p=2(3.14)\hbar/L$. Thus, it seems there is information contained in p . If $\ln(W)$ is information, then for a free particle $W=\exp(ipx)$ and $\ln(\exp(ipx)) = ipx$, so ipx is information. A change in information is ip . Thus, for the general $W(x)$ case, one would expect a change in information to be $\langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ or:

$$(-i) d \ln(W) /dx = \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle \quad ((4))$$

It seems that similar ideas may apply to $\exp(-iEt)$. For a free particle $\ln(\exp(-iEt)) = -iEt$ seems to represent information i.e. time resolution based on E . $d/dt(-iEt) = -iE$ so the information change is proportional to E . One may try to extend these ideas to $W(x,t)$. If $W(x,t) = W(x)\exp(-iEave t)$ one has similar ideas except E is replaced with $Eave$ which represents the resonance energy and is not merely average kinetic energy at each x .

Conditional Averages and Singularities

The conditional probability $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ ((5)) may be used to calculate averages at a point x , such as $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ and $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle$. The latter satisfies: $1/2m \langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle + V(x) = E$. It may be noted that such averages may be purely complex such as $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ for a bound state and may also have singularities due to $W(x)$ in ((5)). Such singularities, however, may not be problematic as one usually forms the measurable average:

Sum over p $P(x) f(p) P(p/x)$ where $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ for a bound state.

$W(x)$ in $P(x)$ cancels $W(x)$ in the denominator of $P(p/x)$, eliminating any issues. A question arises, however,: Why does one need two kinds of averages i.e. Sum over p $f(p)P(p/x)$ and Sum over p $f(p) P(p/x) P(x)$? This is equivalent to the question: Why does one need a wavefunction $W(x)$ and a spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$? Traditionally, only $W^*(x)W(x)$ was recognized as a probability, but we argue $W(x)$ is a relative conditional probability. $P(p/x)$ as a conditional probability only yields the probability for a momentum p if one is at x , it does not indicate the probability to be at x . For the free particle case, two ideas were introduced. First, an $\exp(ipx)$ was used to keep track of the "resolution" present or ipx the information. This requires a function which depends on p and x and not a constant. Nevertheless, overall spatial probability should be a real, constant number. Using $\exp(ipx)$ which has a modulus of 1 allows for this real number to be obtained. The same idea holds for $W(x)$ and $W^*(x)W(x)$, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue there exists a spatial resolution associated with each momentum p in both classical and quantum mechanics. In classical physics, however, the resolution is usually no manifest i.e. there is no "resolution error" in classical mechanical calculations even when they are extended to stochastic motion.

We use the Lorentz invariant $Et - px$ to quantify this resolution and suggest $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ for a free particle based on a statistical probability with modulus 1 i.e. an equal probability for a constant p particular to be at any x .

We argue that $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i\sin(px)$ accounts for two types of probability cycles or flows. $\cos(px)$ is associated with $pp/2m$ -time cycling and $\sin(px)$ with space-spatial flux or momentum cycling or flow. These may also be thought of as information flows with $pp/2m$ and p being two kinds of information flow rates. It may be noted that $\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$ squared is not $\langle pp \text{ at } x \rangle$ as the two

flows are separate. (There is a link, however, given that $\cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px) = 1$.) Each type of information flow is linked to “resolution” pockets e.g. L for $\exp(ipx)$ where $p = 2(3.13)\hbar/L$ with each containing distinct positive and negative regions establishing the frequency of the flow. These lead to interference as one adds other components in order to establish a new resolution for both the energy-time and space-position components.

We also argue that momentum is related to information, in fact for a free quantum particle $\ln(\exp(ipx)) = ipx$ so $-i\hbar d/dx$ i.e. a change in information is p . We argue that a similar idea should hold for the wavefunction of a bound system i.e. $-i\hbar d/dx \ln(W) = \langle p \text{ ave at } x \rangle$ where $\ln(W)$ is information.

References

1. <https://phys.org/news/2015-07-macroscopic-quantum-phenomena-ice.html>